

Effect of N and carbofuran on GM and SB infestation, Badeggi, Nigeria, 1984 wet season. ^a

Treatment	GM damage (% onion shoots)	SB-damaged stems (%)	Yield components and total yield		
			Tillers/hill	Panicles/hill	Yield (t/ha)
N level (kg/ha)					
0	4.2 a	35.3 a	7.3 b	6.8 b	2.59 a
50	4.6 a	36.4 ab	8.8 a	8.1 a	2.12 a
100	4.8 a	39.3 bc	9.5 a	8.7 a	2.13 a
150	1.2 b	40.1 c	9.8 a	8.7 a	2.82 a
Carbofuran application ^b (1.0 kg ai/ha)					
1	6.0 cd	39.7 b	9.3 a	8.4 a	2.19 a
30	4.7 abc	31.6 ab	8.1 a	7.5 a	2.71 a
60	5.6 bcd	38.3 ab	9.3 a	8.7 a	2.58 a
1 and 30	3.6 a	35.3 a	9.3 a	8.1 a	2.88 a
30 and 60	4.1 ab	34.5 a	8.6 a	7.7 a	2.83 a
Untreated	7.2 d	41.0 b	8.5 a	1.3 a	2.51 a

^a Separation of means in a column by DMRT at the 5% level. ^b Days after transplanting.

stems from 20 hills/plot at 10 d before harvest.

GM and SB damage increased with applied N, but the number of tillers/hill and panicles/hill did not increase significantly beyond 0 kg N/ha. Yield did not differ significantly at different N levels (see table).

Applying carbofuran significantly influenced GM and SB damage. Applying carbofuran at 1 and 30 DT significantly reduced GM damage. SB damage was significantly reduced with applications at 1 and 30 DT or 30 and 60 DT. There were no significant differences in yield components or total yield (see table). *ℒ*

Effect of insecticides and variety on stem borer (SB) incidence

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We studied the effect of some insecticides and varieties on SB incidence at Badeggi in 1983 wet season. The field trial was in a split-plot randomized block design with four replications. Twenty-one-day-old FARO 11 and FARO 13 seedlings were transplanted in 25-m² plots at 25- × 25-cm spacing. Insecticides were applied 10, 30, 50, and 70 d after transplanting (DT). Deadhearts due to *Diopsis*

thoracica infestation in each plot were recorded 40 DT. Bored stems from *Maliarpha separatella* infestation were assessed by dissecting 20 randomly selected hills from each plot at 10 d before harvest (see table).

Carbofuran controlled *D. thoracica* most effectively, followed by BHC and decamethrin. Number of bored stems did not significantly differ among insecticide treatments. Carbofuran-treated plots had significantly fewer borers per plant than other plots, and yield was significantly higher.

FARO 11 had more deadhearts than FARO 13, but the difference was insignificant. FARO 11 had significantly more borers per plant. *ℒ*

Influence of N fertilizer on the population development of brown planthopper (BPH)

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We studied BPH *Nilaparvata lugens* biotype 2 reactions to different levels of N fertilizer on selected rices. BPH reared on IR26 were tested on susceptible IR26; Utri Rajapan, tolerant with no antibiosis; Triveni, moderate tolerance and antibiosis; and IR60, high antibiosis.

The N solution was prepared by mixing 125 g of ammonium sulfate containing 20% N in 375 ml water. In each of 2 clay pots lined with polyethylene bags and containing 2.5 kg

Effect of insecticides and varieties on SB incidence, Badeggi, Nigeria, 1983 wet season.

Insecticide	Treatment		Deadhearts 40 DT (%)	Bored stems at harvest (%)	Borers (no/20 hills)	Grain yield (t/ha)
	Formulation	Rate (kg ai/ha)				
BHC	20 EC	2.00	9	22	32	3.3
Decamethrin	2.5 EC	0.50	9	20	29	3.3
Diazinon	60 EC	2.00	21	22	28	2.1
Isoprocarb	75 WP	1.33	13	21	20	2.6
Carbofuran	10G	1.00	4	19	13	3.9
Control			17	22	32	2.8
LSD (P=0.05)			10	ns	10	0.6
Variety						
FARO 13			10	19	19	3.3
FARO 11			14	23	33	2.9
LSD (P=0.05)			ns	2	6	ns
Interaction (P=0.05)			14	ns	ns	ns

1. BPH weight on selected varieties grown under different N fertilizer rates, IIRRI.